

Figure S1. Genotypes of associated SNPs in candidate genes related to **a** plumage coloration and **b** elevation. Sites are shown as rows and individuals as columns, grouped by phenotype with colors corresponding to figure 1a. Individuals homozygous for the reference allele are shown in beige, homozygous for the alternative in orange, heterozygotes are intermediate, and white cells represent missing data.

Figure S3. Genome-wide associations with body color. Significantly associated SNPs shown in orange ($p < 1 \times 10^{-6}$). Scaffolds ordered by size.

Figure S4. Heterozygosity across candidate elevation genes for individuals at high (blue) and low (orange) elevation, or with and without a crown patch respectively. Coding regions are shown as thick gray lines and associated SNPs are shown as black dots.